

A DISTINCTIVE FEATURE OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IS ITS FOCUS ON ACHIEVING A SPECIFIC PRACTICAL GOAL

АДИЛЬХАНОВА К.Р.

магистрант Восточно Казахстанского Университета им. С.Аманжолова

Научный руководитель: **ФЕДОСОВА С.А.** кандидат филологических наук, профессор кафедры иностранных языков и переводческого дела Восточно Казахстанского Университета им. С.Аманжолова

Abstract: *Project-based learning occupies a special place in higher education, allowing students to acquire knowledge not achieved through traditional teaching methods. This is possible because students make their own choices and demonstrate initiative. From this perspective, a good project should: have practical value; involve students in independent research; be equally unpredictable both during the process and at its completion; be flexible in the direction of the work and the pace of its completion; offer the possibility of solving current problems.*

Kew words: *project, discuss, topics, preparation, language, lessons, students, teachers, higher education.*

Using the project method in foreign language lessons requires a competent approach and careful preparation on the part of both students and teachers. To organize project-based learning for middle school students, it is necessary, first, to clarify the basic features of the project method.

Project-based learning occupies a special place in higher education, allowing students to acquire knowledge not achieved through traditional teaching methods. This is possible because students make their own choices and demonstrate initiative. From this perspective, a good project should: have practical value; involve students in independent research; be equally unpredictable both during the process and at its completion; be flexible in the direction of the work and the pace of its completion; offer the possibility of solving current problems; provide students with the opportunity to learn according to their abilities; facilitate the development of student abilities in solving a wider range of problems; and facilitate interaction between students.

As an example, in English class, we discuss problematic topics such as: "What is friendship?" "What is the difference between a psychologist and a psychiatrist?" A presentation on "My future profession" was also given.

An analysis of methodological literature on the problem under study revealed the following:

1) orientation and relevance of students' personal experience. Students conduct research on various phenomena and aspects of life around them: they talk about their families, compile an album of tourist attractions, a newspaper about their class, conduct interviews on various issues, and explore social problems. A well-thought-out and properly developed project gives them the opportunity to use the knowledge they acquired in the classroom for real, personally meaningful purposes in a naturalistic setting outside the classroom;

2) projecting students' activities beyond the classroom (street interviews, visits to various institutions and organizations where foreign-language-speaking employees are present). This tactic helps to shift communication from the academic to the real world;

3) The freedom of action and independence of project participants manifests itself not only in the absence or limited supervision of the teacher at many stages of the project, but also in their independent choice of the project topic, the format of the work, its final result, monitoring, and presentation, as well as in the selection of linguistic resources and the independent search for missing paths and methods of work. All this lends particular meaning to students' learning, helps them see their prospects and goals for the work, and evaluate the results. Thus, they gain the opportunity to demonstrate responsibility in their learning, both to themselves and to their group members;

4) Unlimited opportunities for individualization of student activities and the combination of paired, group, and collaborative work. When the teacher varies these types of work, students develop a certain mobility, flexibility in choosing the most appropriate method, the ability to work in a team, mutual assistance, and mutual enrichment of their educational and personal experiences. An effective approach is the pyramid principle, which consists of students receiving an assignment after a preliminary class discussion, to work through a given learning material individually (at home or in class) and in pairs, followed by a group discussion.

I.A. Bim believes that "a project, its tangible product, usually completes a stage of learning (major or minor), giving it completeness and creating a visible milestone that the student must achieve before moving on.

This helps students acquire self-monitoring and self-assessment skills, which they use to analyze their learning success based on the final product of the project." The product of creative project work can be a collection of essays prepared by students, a written workbook, a wall newspaper, an album, a radio or video program, a presentation, a teleconference, etc.

Based on the nature of the final product of the project activity, the following types of projects can be distinguished:

1. Construction and Practical Projects, such as a collage, an observation diary, "inventing" a game, and describing it.

2. Role-playing projects, such as role-playing a game, optimists and pessimists, a secret theme, dramatization, or writing your own play.

3. Information and Research Projects, such as "The Importance of Learning a Foreign Language," "City Plan."

4. Survey Projects, such as "Sign Language in Different Cultures," "The Need to Use English in My Country."

5. Production Projects, such as "Sights of My City," "Portrait of My Class," and "School Wall Newspaper."

6. Scenario projects — Performance and Organizational projects, such as "Organizing Alumni Reunions," "English Language and Culture Evening," and "Talk Shows."

7. Creative works — such as free literary writing (a fairy tale, short story, comic book, etc.), or a literary translation of a work into a native language.

These types of projects, depending on their subject matter, can be carried out either within the field of foreign language and culture studies or can be interdisciplinary in nature.

Of course, in real-world practice, we most often encounter mixed types of projects that have elements of both research and creative projects, such as practice-oriented and research-oriented projects. Each type of project has its own type of coordination, deadlines, stages, and number of participants. Therefore, when developing a project, it is important to keep in mind the characteristics and features of each type. In our opinion, one of the key features of project-based learning is its focus on achieving a specific, practical goal—a visual presentation of the result, whether it's a drawing, an appliqué, or an essay. Students are given the opportunity to use the language in real-life situations, which undoubtedly contributes to better acquisition and consolidation of foreign language knowledge.

This is where English teachers work closely with their students, discussing interim results and correcting errors in the use of linguistic units. This type of work provides numerous opportunities to apply the grammatical concepts and structures covered. Thus, vocabulary development and expansion continue.

Naturally, students review their essays multiple times, discussing the strengths and weaknesses of each individual essay, offering advice on areas to pay attention to and areas to improve. Suggestions for changes, perhaps additions or deletions, are discussed with the student. Ultimately, the child comes to realize how much they know and how much they can share with their friends in German. The children's fear of the English language disappears and they better understand its logical system.

LITERATURE

1. Новые педагогические и информационные технологии в системе образования: Учебное пособие / [Е. С. Полат](#), М. Ю. Бухаркина, М. В. Моисеева, А. Е. Петров; под ред. [Е. С. Полат](#). — М.: Издательский центр «Академия», 1999—2005.
2. Kilpatric W.H. The Project Method//Teachers College Record.-1918.-19 September/- P.319
3. Современные педагогические и информационные технологии в системе образования: Учебное пособие / [Е. С. Полат](#), М. Ю. Бухаркина, — М.: Издательский центр «Академия», 2007.
4. И.Л. Личностно-ориентированный подход – основная стратегия обновления школы / И.Л. Бим // Иностр. языки в школе. – 2002. – № 2.